

Some Novel Results in Electrochemical Equilibria*

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I feel much honoured to have been invited to deliver the twelfth Sir J. C. Ghosh Memorial lecture. Sir J. C. Ghosh became a hero to me since I read in my college days in the preface of "Thermodynamics" by Max Planck (Preface to the sixth and the seventh editions) the following: "Among the additions to the new edition, I may mention the theory of the lowering of the freezing point of strong electrolytes, which has been developed by J. C. Ghosh of Calcutta. This theory appears at last to clear up the puzzling deviations from Ostwald's dilution law". I was highly elated to find an Indian Chemist's name so honourably mentioned. Personally, I was impressed by some of his lectures, I had the opportunity to listen to and I still remember one of his wise remarks that an Indian as an individual is as good as a European or an American, but collectively say ten Indians together is far less in productivity than say ten English, German or American nationals.

The theoretical work of Ghosh on strong electrolytes in the field of electrochemistry has been a historical landmark in the development of the subject. I therefore consider it opportune to present on this occasion some novel work in electrochemistry and electrochemical equilibria which I have lately done. They will be presented under two separate headings.

Part I: A New Rule for the Positive/Negative Sign of Ion-terms in E. M. F. expression of Electrochemical Cells and its Application to Potentiometric Titration.

In my student days when I had to do potentiometric titrations, I always bothered whether the observed EMF would increase or decrease with progress of titration. It did not take me long to realise that the matter depends on the sign of the ion terms, $(RT/nF) \ln C$ in the EMF equation. It was easy to find from Nernst equation that reversible positive ions added to a positive electrode increase the observed EMF and negative ions decrease it; the opposite thing happens at the negative electrode. I had incorporated this rule for a long time in the popular text book on physical chemistry entitled "Elementary Physical Chemistry" of which I am the author. However, recently I have formalised the matter in the form of a simple rule as discussed below.

1. Sign Rule for Cells & Half-cells

EMF of a Complete Cell: The EMF of a complete cell contains $RT/nF \ln C$ terms which is preceded by either (+) sign or (-) sign (*vide* Eqn. 2). Whether this should be (+) or (-) is given by the following

Sign Rule which can be easily deduced theoretically (Nernst eqn. or reaction isotherm). The rule is: If the positive ions or oxidants are given (+) sign as rank symbol, and negative ions or reductants are given (-) sign as rank symbol, the sign of any $(RT/nF) \ln C$ term in the E.M.F equation of the complete cell is given by the product of the sign of the electrode and the sign of the rank symbol of the ion. i. e.

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{Sign before an Ion-term} \\ \text{of the Ion} \\ \times \text{Polarity of its} \\ \text{Half-cell} \end{array} \right\} \dots (1)$$

The rule is shown in tabular form below:

Electrode i. e. Half-cell	Sign before an Ion-term (Electrode Sign \times Rank Symbol)	
	Positive Ion or oxidant : Rank Symbol (+)	Negative Ion or Reductant : Rank Symbol (-)
(+)	+	-
(-)	-	+

With the help of the above sign rule, and remembering that the E.M.F. of any cell is of the form,

$$\text{EMF (E)} = (E^{\circ}_{+} - E^{\circ}_{-}) (+) \text{ or } (-) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln C \text{ terms} \quad (2)$$

(where E° = standard electrode potential (reduction), the student can write down directly the E. M. F equation of any cell. Some illustrations are given in the following Table (Table 1).

Note that as per our Sign Rule, reversible cations or oxidants are preceded by (+) sign at positive and (-) sign at negative electrode; the opposite happens with anions or reductants.

Half-Cell Potential: In a similar way, we can write down the electrode potential expression of a half-cell (as it is the E.M.F. of a cell where the negative electrode is standard hydrogen electrode whose $E^{\circ} = 0$). Thus half-cell potential $E_{+} = E^{\circ}_{+} (+) \text{ or } (-) \frac{RT}{nF} \ln C$ terms. However for half-cells containing more than one reversible species the above rule can also be applied provided the ion-terms are modified as follows:

$$\text{Ion-terms} = (+) \text{ or } (-) \frac{mRT}{nF} \ln C \dots$$

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TABLE 1

Cell [Right-Hand Half-Cell assumed (+) ve]	E. M. F ($E^\circ = E^\circ_+ - E^\circ_-$)
Cd Cd ⁺⁺ Cu ⁺⁺ Cu	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(Cu^{++}) - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(Cd^{++})$
Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ (s), Cl ⁻ Ag ⁺ Ag	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Ag^+) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Cl^-)$
Pt H ₂ , H ⁺ Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Fe ⁺⁺ Pt	$E^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln(H^+) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Fe^{+++}) - \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Fe^{++})$
Ag Ag ⁺ (a ₁) Ag ⁺ (a ₂) Ag	$+ \frac{RT}{F} \ln(a_2) - \frac{RT}{F} \ln(a_1)$
Ag AgCl(s), Cl ⁻ MnO ₄ ⁻ , Mn ⁺⁺ , H ⁺ Pt	$E^\circ + \frac{8RT}{5F} \ln(H^+) + \frac{RT}{5F} \ln(MnO_4^-)$ $- \frac{RT}{5F} \ln(Mn^{++}) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Cl^-)$
Hg Hg ₂ Cl ₂ (s), Cl ⁻ Quinone (Q), Hydroquinone (H ₂ Q) Pt	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(Q/QH_2) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(H^+) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Cl^-)$

Where *m* = co-efficient of the species in the reduction (or oxidation) equation, and *n* = number of electrons in the same equation. Electrode potential expressions for some half-cells are shown in the following Table.

titrant ; if the product is a positive (+) sign, it indicates a monotonous increase and if a negative (-) sign a decrease with progress of titration. This is tabulated below.

TABLE 2

Half-Cell	Reduction equation	Half-cell Potential Expression
Silver-silver chloride electrode	AgCl(s) + e = Ag(s) + Cl ⁻	$E^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln(Cl^-)$
Quinone-Hydroquinone electrode	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e = C ₆ H ₄ (OH) ₂	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(C_6H_4O_2) + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(H^+) - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln(C_6H_4(OH)_2)$ $= E^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \ln(H^+)$ (when (Q) = (QH ₂))
Dichromate-chromic electrode	Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻ + 6e + 14H ⁺ = 2Cr ³⁺ + 7H ₂ O(l)	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{6F} \ln(Cr_2O_7^{2-}) + \frac{14RT}{6F} \ln(H^+) - \frac{2RT}{6F} \ln(Cr^{3+})$
Permanganate-Manganous electrode	MnO ₄ ⁻ + 8H ⁺ + 5e = Mn ⁺⁺ + 4 H ₂ O (l)	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{5F} \ln \frac{(MnO_4^-)}{(Mn^{++})} + \frac{8RT}{5F} \ln(H^+)$
Permanganate-manganese-dioxide electrode	MnO ₄ ⁻ + 3e + 2H ₂ O (l) = MnO ₂ (s) + 4 OH ⁻	$E^\circ + \frac{RT}{3F} \ln(MnO_4^-) - \frac{4RT}{3F} \ln(OH^-)$
Bismuth-Bismuth oxide electrode	Bi ₂ O ₃ (s) + 3H ₂ O(l) + 6e = 2Bi(s) + 6 OH ⁻	$E^\circ - \frac{RT}{F} \ln(OH^-)$

Note 1. It is to be noted that to obtain *m* and *n* one has to write the reduction (or oxidation) equation of only the half-cell without caring for what is the other half cell. Thus for MnO₄⁻ - Mn⁺⁺ electrode ln(H⁺) has the co-efficient 8RT/5F because 8 is the co-efficient of H⁺ and 5 is the number of electrons in the reduction (or oxidation) equation for the half-cell reaction.

Note 2. It does not matter whether the simplest equation or a multiple of it is written, i. e, whether we write Cu⁺⁺ + 2e = Cu or ½ Cu⁺⁺ + e = ½ Cu.

2. Change of E.M.F during Potentiometric Titration

This rule has a straightforward application in predicting whether an observed EMF will increase or decrease during a potentiometric titration. The rule is : Multiply the sign of the half cell where titration is carried out, with the sign of the oxidation rank of the

Titration done in	Change of E. M. F. on titrating with	
	Simple Cation or an oxidant, Oxidation Rank Sign (+)	Simple anion or a reductant, Oxidation Rank Sign (-)
Positive Half-cell (+)	(+)	(-)
Negative Half-cell (-)	(-)	(+)

This rule applies to all kinds of titration viz. acid-base, redox, and precipitation. Some examples are cited below.

Example : *Acid-Base titration.* Cell representation : (-) Glass H || Calomel (+) ; Titrant : Alkali

We are titrating here with OH^- [Symbol (—)], in the negative half-cell (—); since $(-)\times(-)=(+)$, we predict that the observed E.M.F. monotonically increase during titration.

Example 2 : *Redox titration.* (i) Titration with permanganate ion (ii) Titration with titanous ion

(i) Since MnO_4^- has a positive oxidation rank (+), our rule predicts that the observed E.M.F. will increase with progress of titration if the titration vessel is the positive half-cell and would decrease in a negative half-cell. (ii) The opposite is true in titration with titanous (or ferrous) ion because being a reductant its oxidation rank is negative (—).

Example 3 : *Precipitation titration.* Suppose we titrate Cl^- ion by adding silver nitrate, the indicator electrode being Ag/AgCl . According to our rule the titrant is a simple (+) ion. Therefore, if the titration is carried out at a positive electrode, the E. M. F would increase during titration and just the opposite would happen at a negative electrode.

This rule is always algebraically exact but it makes simple physical sense if the cell representation coincides with the actual polarity of electrodes of the real cell (i. e. use of negative voltage is to be avoided as far as possible). The rule thus provides a quick means to predict the direction of E.M.F change during any potentiometric titrations.

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Part II : Application of Hard-Soft-Acid-Base (HSAB) Principle to some Anomalous Equilibria in Organic Media.

Introduction

In any concept of acid-base strength is inherent the intuitive notion that a strong acid can largely displace a weak acid from its salt ; and also a similar situation with respect to bases. As a matter of fact this displacement power was in earlier days taken as a quantitative measure of acid-base strength. The results were fairly consistent.

However, ambiguities arose as soon as reactions were studied in organic solvents. A simple illustration is the observed reversal of order of titration exponents of indicators in organic solvents. Many such cases are recorded in the literature, though it is the general impression that the relative order of indicator basicity remains unchanged by a change of solvent.

Displacement of a Strong Base by a Weak Base : Lately, we have come across cases in organic solvents which do violence to this conventional notion of relative acid-base strength¹. Let us take for example the following reaction where a dye base (I) (usually colourless) reacts with a polymeric sulphonic acid in say, benzene medium.

This is a normal reaction between a weak base and a strong acid and the equilibrium as expected lies predominantly to the right hand side ; on mixing the two solutions an intense colour corresponding to the dye cation (II) develops. However, if the sodium salt of the sulphonic acid is used in place of the acid itself the same type of facile reaction takes place evidently according to the following equation (eqn. 2).

This is however a highly unexpected reaction where the weak carbinol base is displacing the strongest base caustic soda. The author first came across such reactions when studying the dye interaction test for detection and estimation of anionic endgroups in polymers². The reaction takes place smoothly even at concentrations as low as $N/100,000$. It is extremely easy to give visual demonstration of the above reaction by the colour formation. It is to be noted that the reaction runs in the backward direction in aqueous medium, the well-known colour discharge of triphenylmethane dyes in alkali being good examples. It is to be further noted that the sodium salt need not be a polymer. An anionic detergent soluble in the organic solvent responds equally well to the above reaction.

It follows from equation (2) that if NaOH could be removed from the system the equilibrium could be displaced almost totally to the right. This expectation from theory is easily fulfilled experimentally. On addition of a suitable ion-exchange resin (acid-form) or solid hydrated oxalic acid or citric acid the equilibrium gets shifted to the right as seen by the intensification of colour. We are studying the possibility of

applying the above reaction for quantitative estimation of anionic detergents.

Not only benzene but many other hydrophobic solvents can be used as the above reaction medium. Even alcohol can be used but only with those few dyes whose carbinol base has not the cationic colour in alcohol (for example 'red' methylene blue and 'red' thionine blue).

Displacement of a Strong Acid by a Weak Acid: The counterpart of the above reaction, viz. the displacement of a strong acid by a weak acid is also common in organic solvents. Such reactions are easily observed² between an amine endgroup and a colourless dye acid (III) of the eosin class in benzene according to the following equation.

There is nothing unusual in the above reaction, this being simply the neutralisation of an acid by an amine. The most surprising thing however was the fact² that the reaction takes place (colour develops) in an equally facile way if a polymer having as endgroup an ammonium salt of a strong acid is used in place of the free amine evidently according to the following equation.

This is a most remarkable reaction where a weak organic acid is displacing one of the strongest acids known, viz. HCl. Still more surprising is the fact that the reaction takes place³ even if the carbonyl group is esterified, i. e. the phenolic dye (V) displaces the strong HCl in benzene or similar solvents (equation 5)

A visual demonstration of the above reaction would be to mix the dye extract with the salt solution in benzene when an intense colouration is seen to take place. Even a simple nitrophenol can be used as the dye since the anion of such compounds are strongly coloured¹. The reaction would be as follows.

...(6)

The reaction takes place smoothly even at thousandth normal concentration or still lower. The equilibrium can be shifted towards the right by removing the strong acid. This is easily done in benzene by adding a few pellets of NaOH leading to intensification of colour. A possible application of this reaction would be in the analysis of benzene-soluble salts.

The type of reaction shown in equation (4) was also observed by Steigman and Lorentz³ when they brought together bromophthalein magenta and a quaternary ammonium salt in benzene. They were naturally puzzled and thought that the alkali from the glass wall was probably an intermediate reactant. They took great pains to disprove this idea but was under the general impression that the reaction is basically between an organic base and the above-mentioned phenolic dye which was catalysed by the quaternary ammonium salt. Even Davis⁴ the pioneer worker in the field of dye acid—organic base interaction, prepared the quaternary ammonium salt via the hydroxide as she did not anticipate a reaction of the type shown in equation (4) or (5) to go towards right probably because of its apparent impossibility.

Theory (HSAB principle): It is evident that our intuitive notion of acid-base strength irrespective of the solvent gets a rude jolt by such observations. Two kinds of rationalization are possible. It may be thought that a kind of leveling effect in reverse takes place in organic solvents such that all acids become weak, their strength being reduced to a more or less same level due to solvent effect. On general ground this is not an appealing idea particularly as it hardly throws any light into such unexpected behaviour.

Alternatively, this unusual course of reaction may be thought of as consistent with the hard-soft-acid-base (HSAB) principle⁵. The dye ions being big and highly polarisable may be considered soft and so they have an innate affinity for their soft counterparts, which is the driving force towards the above unexpected direction. However, it is difficult to see how HI could be displaced according to equation (4) to (6), as the polarisable iodide ion is supposed to be a highly soft base. May be, the organic anions are far softer. It would be highly interesting to study simple non-dye compounds under

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the above conditions. Anyway, there is no escape from the fact that an absolute order of acid-base strength is an unattainable goal and extraneous factors which may not be directly linkable with the acidity or dipole moment of the solvent, might also play an important role.

Acknowledgement

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